

USE OF BAGASSE ASH WITH LIME SLUDGE AND GYPSUM TO IMPROVE THE PROPERTIES OF CONCRETE (COMPRESSIVE STRENGTH OF M20 CEMENT CUBE)

Neha Digge¹, Shankar Prasad¹

¹Students of Civil Engineering
Nitte Meenakshi Institute of Technology, Yelahanka Bangalore, Karnataka, India

Abstract

To strike balance between the developments in infrastructure and prevention of the environment from contamination by reusing the industrial wastes. With the use of industrial waste residue, apart from improving properties of concrete, main benefits come from saving natural resources and energy, as well as protecting the environment. The feasibility of using sugarcane Bagasse Ash (SBA), a finely ground waste product from the sugarcane industry, keeping the quantity of gypsum (10%) and lime sludge (20%) constant and using it as partial replacement for cement in conventional concrete is to be examined. The tests are conducted as per Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) codes to evaluate the stability, workability and strength of SBA for replacements of cement in the concrete. Concrete mix is prepared for M20 grade concrete.

In the first step we tested the properties of all the materials that are to be used. Then the Mix was Design for M-20 grade concrete and casting of moulds (i.e Cubes) was carried out. Without replacing cement, fine aggregate & coarse aggregate for comparison.

Then partial replacement of cement with varying percentage (%) of Bagasse Ash, keeping the percentages of Lime Sludge & Gypsum constant, for M20 grade was carried out.

Compressive strengths (3, 7, and 28 days) are determined. The results with the addition of sugarcane bagasse ash, lime sludge and gypsum are checked and strengths in all cases are tested.

Such cement can be used for rigid pavements and concrete

Keywords : Bagasse Ash, Lime Sludge ,Gypsum, Compressive strength

INTRODUCTION :

The most common cement is used is ordinary Portland cement. Out of the total production, ordinary Portland cement accounts for about 80-90 percent. Many countries are using pozzolanic materials in concrete structures for improving compressive strength and reducing the cost of concrete. Many pozzolanic materials such as bagasse ash, fly ash, silica fume, rice husk ash, palm oil fuel ash, etc., have been improved and used to replace cement in concrete. There is the additional bonus that these materials are waste products to begin with which would otherwise incur a disposal or environmental cost. By incorporating pozzolanic materials into concrete is also adding value to these products.

India is the second largest sugar producing country in the world. It contributes about 20% of the total sugar industry in the world and accounts for about 15% of the global production. Thus producing large amount of waste that has to be disposed off. . So here comes the picture of “Alternative Building Materials”.

The objective of this study was to investigate the properties of bagasse ash in concrete with varying percentages of bagasse ash and with constant percentages of lime sludge & gypsum. So here comes the picture of “Alternative Building Materials”.

2. MATERIALS FOR TEST

2.1 Cement: In this experiment 53 grade Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC) with brand name “BIRLA SUPER 53 Grade”. The cement used was fresh and without any lumps available in local market is used for the experiment. The cement used has been tested for various Proportions as per IS 4031-1988 and found to be

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The physical properties of cement given by the company and tested are:

Particulars	Experimental Results	As per Standard
1.Setting Time		
a.Initial (minutes)	50min	30min
b.Final (minutes)	8hrs	10hrs
2.Temperature	25	25±2°c
3.Specific Gravity	3.10	3.15

2.2 Coarse Aggregates : Crushed angular granite stone of 20 mm and 10 mm size from a local source was used as coarse aggregate. The coarse aggregate used in the experiment were 50% 10mm & 50% of the total 20mm down size. The specific gravity of the coarse aggregate was:

Particulars	Coarse Aggregate
Specific gravity	2.66

2.2 Fine aggregate : River sand was used as fine aggregate. The sand used for the experiment was locally available and was confirmed to zone-II. The specific gravity of the fine aggregate was:

Particulars	Fine Aggregate (Sand)
Specific gravity	2.62

Bagasse Ash: Sugar-cane bagasse is one such fibrous waste-product of the sugar refining industry, along with ethanol vapor. Bagasse ash mainly contains aluminium ion and silica. Bagasse ash has been considered for having pozzolanic material like fly ash or any other conventional pozzolana. It is consider that the material may be used locally as a mortar, especially in rural areas where availability is high. This helps to increase the strength and is also economical.

Particulars	Bagasse ash
Specific gravity	2.42

Gypsum: is a soft sulphate composed of Calcium sulphate dehydrate. Gypsum is primarily used as a finish for walls and ceilings, and is known in

construction as drywall Gypsum blocks used like cement blocks in building construction. Gypsum mortar is an ancient mortar used in building construction. A binder in fast-dry tennis court clay. This can be used as a binder material.

2.6 Lime Sludge: Lime sludge is a waste product which is produced during the manufacturing of paper. It is a very fine precipitated CaCO₃ particles with few impurities. But major composition of lime sludge is calcium carbonate.

3. USES OF WASTE FROM THE MANUFACTURING INDUSTRY : (SBA and Lime sludge)

3.1 Uses Of Bagasse Ash:

Sugarcane bagasse ash is a byproduct of sugar factories found after burning sugarcane bagasse which itself is found after the extraction of all economical sugar from sugarcane. The disposal of this material is already causing environmental problems around the sugar factories. On the other hand, the boost in construction activities in the country created shortage in most of concrete making materials especially cement, resulting in an increase in price. This study examined the potential use of sugarcane bagasse ash as a partial cement replacement material.

Uses:

- Used in construction industry for partial replacement of cement
- Used in tile making industry
- Used to stabile compacted soil
- Used in manufacturing of bricks

3.2 Uses Of Lime Sludge:

Lime sludge is a byproduct for the paper industry. Reusing of this has turned out economical and environmental friendly. When lime sludge is dewatered and dried, it is mostly calcium carbonate, or the same substance chemically as limestone. Dried lime sludge is fine grained and was classified as a silt size material with a large available surface area.

Uses:

- Replacement for mined limestone in cement kilns.
- Neutralization of acidic industrial wastewater.
- Dust control on gravel roads.
- Use as fill material in road construction.
- Used in construction industry
- Reused in paper mills by converting into quick lime.

4. NEED OF SUGARCANE BAGASSE ASH (SCBA) USAGE:

- Each ton of cement produces approximately about one ton of CO₂ and cement industry is responsible for the emission of about 5% of CO₂ worldwide.
- Brings positive effect to the environment.
- When used as replacement for cement in concrete, it reduces the problem associated with their disposal.
- Decrease in the emission of greenhouse gases. This also enhances the strength of the concrete when used effectively

- Final setting time – 20min
- Origin of raw material purchased– Iran

Parameter	Units	Values
Silicon dioxide	%	0.34
Aluminum oxide	%	0.09
Iron oxide	%	0.09
Calcium oxide	%	32.60
Magnesium oxide	%	0.56
Sulphur trioxide	%	44.90
Potassium oxide	%	0.03
Loss on ignition	%	211.22

5. CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF MATERIALS USED FOR EXPERIMENT :

5.1 Bagasse Ash Waste From Sugar Factory (all in wt.%)

Parameter	Units	Values
Silicon dioxide	%	62.43
Aluminum oxide	%	4.38
Iron oxide	%	6.98
Calcium oxide	%	11.8
Magnesium oxide	%	2.51
Sulphur oxide	%	1.48
Potassium oxide	%	3.53
Loss on ignition	%	4.73

5.1 Lime Sludge Waste From Paper Mills

Parameter	Unit	Value
pH	-	10.93
Water holding Capacity	%	70.43
Organic carbon	%	0.12
Conductivity	mS/cm	2.86
Calcium carbonate	%	66.5
Chloride	ppm	560.0
Available phosphorous	ppm	0.078
Available calcium	ppm	494.0
Available sodium	ppm	30.0
Available potassium	ppm	3.7

5.2 Gypsum

- Colour – 95% WHITE
- Initial setting time – 9.5mim

6. MIX PROPORTION FOR THE TEST

The concrete mix is designed as per the guidelines given in the various Indian standards namely IS 10262 – 1982, IS 456-2000 and SP 23.

6.1 For standard M-20 (0% Bagasse Ash) :

Cement	Coarse	Fine	W/c	Bagasse ash
1.241kg	4.48kg	2.367kg	0.55	0 %

6.2 Varying The Percentage Of Bagasse Ash To 10%

S.No	Materials	Values in %
1	Bagasse ash	10%
2	Gypsum	10%
3	Lime Sludge	20%
4	Cement	60%
5	Coarse Aggregate	Unaltered
6	Fine Aggregate	Unaltered
7	W/C	0.55

Material Calculation For 3 Cubes		
S.No	Materials	Values in kg
1	Bagasse ash	0.373
2	Gypsum	0.373
3	Lime Sludge	0.744
4	Cement	2.404
5	Coarse Aggregate	13.402
6	Fine Aggregate	7.101
7	W/C	0.55

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6.3 Varying The Percentage Of Bagasse Ash To 30%:

S.No	Materials	Values in %
1	Bagasse ash	30%
2	Gypsum	10%
3	Lime Sludge	20%
4	Cement	40%
5	Coarse Aggregate	Unaltered
6	Fine Aggregate	Unaltered
7	W/C	0.55

Material Calculation For 3Cubes

S.No	Materials	Values in kg
1	Bagasse ash	1.117
2	Gypsum	0.373
3	Lime Sludge	0.744
4	Cement	1.489
5	Coarse Aggregate	13.402
6	Fine Aggregate	7.101
7	W/C	0.55

6.4 Varying The Percentage Of Bagasse Ash To 50%

S.No	Materials	Values in %
1	Bagasse ash	50%
2	Gypsum	10%
3	Lime Sludge	20%
4	Cement	20%
5	Coarse Aggregate	Unaltered
6	Fine Aggregate	Unaltered
7	W/C	0.55

Material Calculation For 3 Cubes

S.No	Materials	Values in kg
1	Bagasse ash	2.019
2	Gypsum	0.373
3	Lime Sludge	0.744
4	Cement	0.892
5	Coarse Aggregate	13.402
6	Fine Aggregate	7.101
7	W/C	0.55

7. Mixing and Casting :

Mixing was done as per the standard procedures. Care was taken while mixing the concrete. Bagasse ash was taken in various proportions to replace Cement.. Three cubes were prepared for each percentage variation for 3, 7 and 21days. A total of 36 cubes were prepared in a mould of size 15cm x15cm x 15cm for compressive testing. Curing process is designed primarily to keep the concrete moist by controlling the loss of moisture from the body of concrete, During the given period in which

it gains strength. The water for curing should be tested for every 3, 7 & 28 days and the temperature must be at $27\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$.

8. TESTS:

For cube test 150*150*150 mm moulds were used. Total of 36 cubes were prepared including controlled concrete and concrete mixed with bagasse ash in different proportions from 10%, 30% and 50% and with constant percentages of gypsum 20% and lime sludge 10% of the volume of Cement. The samples were tested for its compressive strength with standard apparatus at three different curing intervals of 3 days, 7 days and 28 days. The results were collected and presented with a graphical mode

9. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

All the cube samples were tested for compressive strength.

- Increase in the percentage of bagasse ash beyond 30% show no improvement in strength and fails to meet the standards.
- The percentage of Bagasse ash of 10% shows that it is workable as well as the load carrying capacity is similar to the standard concrete mix (without any replacements). But further changes shows failure.
- The concept of mixing Bagasse ash (waste from the sugar industry) and lime sludge (waste from the paper mills) is environmental friendly method for disposal of solid waste in the country. This study shows a potential towards the concept of green concrete or environmental friendly concrete.

9.1 Special Aspects:

- The whole process is simple.
- It does not need any new machinery.
- The waste produced in the nearby locality can be used efficiently.
- It is environmental friendly.
- It is cost effective.

9.2 GRAPHS

Graph 1: 3days compression test.

Graph 2: 7days compression test.

Graph 3: 28days compression test.

10. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the experimental data received after a wide range of samples with different proportions of bagasse ash being tested, following conclusions are made,

- We can effectively use Bagasse ash & Lime sludge the end-product from the sugar and paper industry to avoid environmental pollution.
- We can replace about 10% of cement by Bagasse ash without sacrificing the strength of concrete.

- The graphical representation shows the theoretical and experimental deflection.
- This fails in compressive strength after certain changes and does not meet the standards after the variation of bagasses ash at about 30%.
- The idea of utilizing the Bagasse ash in concrete production greatly reduces the water and land pollution that would otherwise occur due to disposal of the Bagasse ash on land That the strength is in not greatly affected by the replacement.
- It avoids the general techniques of disposal like landfill

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